

SURFACE WATER MANAGEMENT TO AUGMENT WATER RESOURCES ALONG VRISHABHAVATHI RIVER

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Abstract

Vrishabhavathi Watershed is a constituent of the Arkavathi River Basin, Bangalore Urban and Ramanagara District and covers an area of 360.62 Km², representing seasonally dry tropical climate. In Vrishabhavathi catchment Vrishabhavathi River is the main source of surface water source which is tributary of River Arkavathy, which joins the Cauvery River at Mekedatu near sangama. Earlier this holy water was mainly used for agricultural purpose and drinking purpose. The Catchment lies in Bangalore urban and Bangalore rural area. The stream which flows in urban region receives a lot of waste water released from industrial and domestic areas. The water is highly polluted and generates lot of foul smell in the flow stretch in urban region. An attempt has been made to identify the potential sites for detention ponds along the Vrishabhavathi River which will be used to maintain the acceptable water quality for sewage Irrigation. For this analysis we need the Base map and thematic maps such as Drainage map, Land use /land cover map and Vrishabhavathi River geometry map. Remote sensing and GIS is useful tool to identify the suitable sites for detention ponds along the River. By assigning the weights to point feature in Vrishabhavathi River geometry map, then calculating suitability indices potential sites for detention ponds are identified .The water stored in the detention ponds are continuously treated with minimum cost and allowed to flow in the downstream for further oxidation. At suitable location water can be lifted up to suitable near water body and used for sewage irrigation.

Keywords: Detention pond, River basin, Landuse/landcover, Geometry map etc.,

1.0 Introduction

The surface water bodies have become dumping yards for industrial effluents and domestic wastes. Many of the rivers and reservoirs are contaminated by these kinds of environmental disturbance. The status of degree of pollution is generally assessed by studying physical, chemical, organic demand and toxic characteristics of water bodies in the river basin. Keeping this in mind the samples are collected at various locations in the river stretch to determine existing surface water quality. In the urban area of this river basin, enormous quantity of ground water is extracted from the bore wells for industrial and construction activities and in the rural area, ground water is extracted for drinking and agricultural activities due to poor quality of river water. Today large numbers of bore wells are being drilled by private enterprises for supplying water through tankers to the city and to the suburban areas. Various fresh water tanks have been dried up due to rapid urbanization and industrialization, which were earlier served as ground water recharge zones. Today dried up tanks have become grounds for dumping of solid and liquid wastes leading to contamination. Therefore groundwater quality monitoring has been become a task for all of us. Groundwater potential zone is an effervescent and vital renewable zone and contributes around 34% of the water supply annually. To meet the local necessitate of the people, exploration of ground water resources requires thorough understanding of various parameters which exert most important influence on aquifer characteristics. In the

present study, GIS software is used for preparation of various thematic layers like lithology, drainage density, lineament density, slope, soil, land use/land cover, geomorphology and rainfall map in raster format with assigned weightage in a spatial field to determine potential zones for groundwater recharge(N S Magesh et.al [1], Jatisankar Bandyopadhyay et.al; [2],Shashank Shekhar et.al; [3], Domingos Pinto et.al; [4],S K Nag et.al; [5])

River water pollution is the major global problem in urban areas. The quality of water is an important aspect to be considered before it is consumed for domestic, industrial and agricultural purpose. Majority of industries in an urban area are water based and a considerable volume of contaminated water will be discharged into the River course from them (Puthenveedu harikumar et al., 2014) [6]. There is an alarming gap between the supply and demand of water which is a threat to human existence on some parts of the globe. It is time to refocus on the reuse of urban wastewater for irrigation and other non potable purposes. Andrew Bradford et.al, 2003[7] conducted studies on waste water irrigation in and around Hubli-Dharward region and that mission was successful. The water quality of the Vrishbhavathi River is below the acceptable range for agricultural purposes even though it is used for that purpose. In earlier days, Vrishbhavathi River was major tributary of Arkavathy, which joins the Cauvery River at sangam. Since it drains from Bangalore urban area it becomes an outlet for the domestic and industrial wastes of that area and today this water is not safe for agricultural plantation activities. There are many major and minor industries functioning in the River basin. Major industries have adopted STP and treated water will be discharged in to the River channel. Minor industries don't have STP and they directly let untreated water in to the River. This leads to the increase of contamination intensity in the Vrishbhavathi River. Deterioration of tanks and drains in the urban territory is the major influencing factor for urban flooding and alteration in water quality. There are only two treatment plants available along the length of the Vrishbhavathi River, which is not sufficient to keep the pollution level under control. Hence, an immediate action has to be taken for identification of potential sites for detention ponds and treatment plants along the River course for cleansing of River. After treatment this water can be used for agricultural and other non-potable purposes. The detention ponds will have a permanent pool of water that fluctuates in response to precipitation and runoff from the contributing areas. The detention ponds can be used for flood control and sewage water treatment [7]. In the first step, Vrishbhavathi River alignment map is prepared in ArcMap platform by the total station survey data and base map. This map shows the longitudinal section points at irregular intervals as a point feature. At each point measure the top width, bottom width and depth of the River. For the study consider all the sections as trapezoidal. In the curves we have measured the cross sectional area and volume by small segmental approach. All these details are entered in the attributes. In the urban region already there are two treatment plants having capacity of 180 MLD of primary and secondary and 75 MLD of tertiary in Rajarajeshwari Arch and Mylasandra regions respectively (BWSSB) [8]. Further there are no treatment plants along the River stretch. After Mylasandra again there are many tributaries that will join the River and which add industrial, agricultural and domestic pollutants. The straight stretch of the River which is having sufficient length, width and proper storage for

detention ponds are identified. Then the detention ponds in the vicinity of the agricultural areas have been located through GIS analysis. After identifying detention ponds' location, a treatment plant is proposed near the bank of the River. Using land use /land cover map, google earth images and information from local government authority, the barren land, industrial area, public parks, forest plantation area and agricultural area and its elevation, which is closer to proposed detention ponds' locations are identified. From the treatment plant, water will be transferred to the elevated storage tank/recharge zone located at a suitable place which satisfies the demand through gravity flow.

2.0 Study Area

The study area of this research is Vrishbhavathi River basin, which falls in Arkavathy catchment. This area lies between latitudes $12^{\circ} 44' 37''$ to $13^{\circ} 2' 31''$ N and longitudes $77^{\circ} 23' 14''$ to $77^{\circ} 34' 59''$ E. The catchment has an area of 360.28 sq. km. The mean annual rainfall of the River basin is 853.56 mm. Vrishabhavathi River is perennial due to the contribution of domestic and industrial effluents. The location of the study area is shown in Fig 2.1.

Fig 2.1 Location map of the study area

3.0 Methodology:

Using morphometric analysis, the total number of streams and drainage density has been calculated. This gives an idea about the network of the drains in the River basin. Using total station survey, the top width, bottom width and depth of the River course were determined at different locations along the River course. From this data, alignment map of the Vrishabhavathi River stretch has been prepared. The cross sectional area is calculated at various locations in the course of the River. From the cross sectional area

and length of the River stretch, the volume of water in that particular stretch has obtained. In the attributes of the map all the details relating to the River dimensions are entered. The straight stretch having more length and width having more storage capacity of water has been identified for detention ponds. The parameters like land use pattern, space availability for setting up treatment plant, tank distance from detention pond site location and sources of pollution are also considered for the analysis. Using these data in attribute table, different thematic maps are generated using ArcGIS software. Based on the weightages and ranks, weightage maps are prepared. These weightage maps are analysed through weighted overlay analysis tool in ArcGIS environment. Weighted overlay analysis gives suitable locations for potential sites for detention ponds and water treatment plants. From the treatment plant water has to be pumped to the elevated storage tanks, which provide water for agricultural activities through channels by gravity. Fig 3.1 shows Methodology adopted for identification of suitable sites for detention ponds.

Fig. 3.1: Methodology adopted for identification of suitable sites for the detention ponds

4.0 Preparation of the influencing parameters map

The following influencing parameters are considered for the identification of suitable locations for detention ponds such as, length of the River stretch, width of the River stretch, depth of the River at various sections, space available for setting up of treatment plants, distance between treatment plant and storage tank, landuse pattern near the detention ponds and sources of pollution. From the total station survey, collect the width, length and elevation at the various cross sectional stretch of the River regime. The entire cross sectional points of stretch are marked as point feature. Each value of influence parameters for respective point feature is entered in attribute table. Using point density tool in ArcGIS software different thematic maps have been prepared.

4.1 Length, Top width and Depth of the River stretch

Using Total station survey the length of the River stretch has been measured. Using point density tool, classification map of length at various cross section stretches is generated. The stretch length measured at various cross sections varied from 14.8 m to 425 m. Based on its influence on suitable site locations for detention ponds, weightages and rankings are assigned. Using Total station survey the width of the River stretch has been measured. Using point density tool, classification map of width at various cross sections of stretches is generated. The top width of River stretch measured at various cross sections are varied from 8m to 52m. Volume of water stored in the detention ponds depends upon the depth of the water at various seasons of a year. The elevations at various cross sections have determined using the Total station. The depth of River at various cross sections has determined from these elevation data. Height of the detention pond bund is based on the depth of the River. Based on the depth provide bund height of 1.5m or 2m. In any case, if bund height more than 2m, flooding will occur in the adjoining lands of the River course. Fig 4.1 shows map for the River stretch length.

4.2 Space availability for setting up of treatment plants

Space is the important criteria for the construction of treatment plants near the detention ponds. Government land and barren land are most suitable for construction of treatment plants since it reduces the cost and also it does not disturb the surrounding areas. If it is a private property or settlements then it will be a problem of re-habitation. Considering a buffer space of 100 m on either side, weightages and rankings are assigned with reference to land use /land cover, google earth image and information from local government authority. Fig 4.1 shows the classification map for availability of space for treatment plants.

4.3 Distance between detention ponds site and storage tanks/recharge zones

Location of elevated storage tank/recharge zone depends upon the distance from the detention pond sites. If distance is more, then water supply cost will be more. If distance is less than 1km then that place is highly suitable. If it is not available then far off distance can also be considered depending upon water demand. Its elevation must be more than the demand areas' elevation. Based on its influence, weightages and rankings are

assigned on the suitable site locations for detention ponds in the River stretch. Fig 4.1 shows the classification map for storage tanks/recharge zones.

4.4 Sources of pollution

Sources of pollution are classified as red, orange, green and white categories as per CPCB guidelines. In the study, 106 industries have identified of above said categories. Also identified major hospitals located along the River. Based on the contribution of pollution level from the source, weightage and ranking have assigned for this parameter. Fig. 4.1 shows the map of sources of pollution along the River.

4.5 Landuse pattern near to detention pond

Land use pattern mainly depends upon the activities of human beings. Throughout the year water will be flowing in the river due to sewage water. Hence the river stretch which is closer to the areas which cultivate perennial, kharif and rabi crops are suitable locations for detention ponds. The water stored in the detention ponds can be supplied to the agricultural fields. Landuse pattern classification map is prepared using the details of landuse/land cover map. As per the influence of landuse pattern on suitable locations of detention ponds, weightage and rankings are assigned. Fig 4.1 shows the classification

map for landuse pattern along the river stretch.

Fig. 4.1 Classification Maps

5.0 Preparation of the weightage maps

Each influencing parameters are weighted according to its strength. For all the parameters weightage and ranking have assigned based on its importance. Based on the weightage and ranks given in the Table 5.1, all the thematic maps are reclassified using reclassify tool in ArcGIS software to obtain weightage map. The suitability of location for detention ponds of present study area can be divided into four grades namely poor, moderate, good and excellent. The rank given for excellent is 4, for good it is 3, for moderate it is 2 and for poor it is 1. All these maps are in raster format shown in Fig 5.1.

Table 5.1 Weightages and rankings assigned for thematic maps to identify the suitable locations for detention ponds

Thematic maps	Map weightage (%)	Map features	Rank	Suitability condition for Detention ponds location
River stretch length classification map	20	<100m	1	Poor
		100m-200m	2	Moderate
		200m-300m	3	Good
		>300m	4	Excellent
River stretch width classification map	15	<10m	1	Poor
		10m-20m	2	Moderate
		20m-30m	3	Good
		>30m	4	Excellent
River depth classification map	15	<3.5m	1	Poor
		3.5-5m	2	Moderate
		5-7.0m	3	Good
		>7.0m	4	Excellent
Tank distance classification map	10	>4km	1	Poor
		2km-4km	2	Moderate
		1km-2km	3	Good
		<1km	4	Excellent
Space availability classification map	10	Settlements	1	Poor
		Private land	2	Moderate
		Barren/Fallow land	3	Good
		Government land	4	Excellent
Landuse pattern classification map	10	Settlements	1	Poor
		Grassing area/Wasteland	2	Moderate
		Kharif season crops	3	Good
		Horticultural crops/Rabi season crops	4	Excellent
Sources of pollution map	20	Red category	4	Excellent
		Orange category	3	Good
		Green category/Hospital	2	Moderate
		White category	1	Poor
River depth classification map	15	<3.5m	1	Poor
		3.5-5m	2	Moderate
		5-7.0m	3	Good
		>7.0m	4	Excellent

Tank distance classification map	10	>4km	1	Poor
		2km-4km	2	Moderate
		1km-2km	3	Good
		<1km	4	Excellent
Space availability classification map	10	Settlements	1	Poor
		Private land	2	Moderate
		Barren/Fallow land	3	Good
		Government land	4	Excellent
Landuse pattern classification map	10	Settlements	1	Poor
		Grassing area/Wasteland	2	Moderate
		Kharif season crops	3	Good
		Horticultural crops/Rabi season crops	4	Excellent
Sources of pollution map	20	Red category	4	Excellent
		Orange category	3	Good
		Green category/Hospital	2	Moderate
		White category	1	Poor

6.0 Detention ponds

The obtained weightage maps are superimposed by weighted overlay method in ArcGIS environment with reference to map weightage and ranks are tabulated to identify the suitable locations for detention pond in the River stretch for sustainable management of River basin. The obtained weighted overlay map has been classified into four categories such as excellent, good, moderate, and poor. From the study, stretch of poor and moderate zones is good for construction of smaller and medium size detention ponds as well as treatment plants. Stretch of good and excellent zones are good sites for construction of large and very large size of detention ponds as well as treatment plants. Fig.6.1 shows potential site locations for detention ponds. The weir or barrage is designed as per IS 6966- Part 1, 2001(Indian standard hydraulic design of barrages and weirs)[9]. The map of detention pond locations and groundwater potential zone classifications are shown in Fig 6.1. The map of detention pond location and flood prone zone classifications are shown in Fig 6.1. Even though Fig 6.1 shows the groundwater prospective zone classification and location of detention ponds, in Fig 6.1 shows a particular minor irrigation tanks to receive treated water from detention ponds (Aravinda P T, Ph.D Thesis) [10]. Table 6.1 shows the details of detention pond and storage tank/recharge zone.

Fig. 5.1 Weightage Maps

Fig. 6.1 Decision making maps

7.0 Conclusions:

The study was aimed at improving the water quality and ground water potential zone. The detention ponds are proposed to collect contaminated water in the River and treat to the required level. The treated water is utilized for groundwater recharge and irrigation. About seven control parameters are identified for determining the location of detention ponds. The GIS analysis has revealed different locations for detention ponds which are to be constructed in the near future based on the ground survey and priority. It also reveals that by constructing detention ponds seasonal flooding can be reduced in the low lying areas of the urban region. In the urban region fourteen detention ponds with inline treatment plants are required. This reduces the burden on the treatment plant constructed near the

detention ponds in the lower reaches of River. Fourteen detention ponds are required in the lower reaches also. The treatment plant brings the water quality to the agriculture water quality standards. The proposed detention ponds and treatment plants will certainly bring down the water pollution and eradicate seasonal floods occurring at many places in the River stretch. The proposal also provides for lifting treated water to suitable minor irrigation tanks augment water resource for agriculture and groundwater recharge.

Table 6.1 Details of detention pond and recharge zone /storage tank

Sl no	Name/Place of existing tank	Area of tank (km ²)	Perimeter of tank(m)	Elevation of existing tank in (m)	Detention pond no	Volume of water stored in detention pond(ha-m)	Distance between detention pond and identified tank (m)	Elevation of identified location of detention pond(m)	Difference in elevation between detention pond and tank (m)
1	Kempambudhi Kere	129989.01	1818.98	876.83	6	1.16	2272.60	843.60	33.23
2	Doddanna Industrial Estate, Lake 6	14976.11	514.48	884.15	2	0.33	534.39	854.88	29.27
3	Near Byraveshwaranagara, Lake 7	26256.91	741.47	894.82	1	0.21	1466.69	867.38	27.44
4	Ballehannu Kere	25756.18	776.97	865.85	3	1.89	1036.49	843.90	21.95
5	Near Hosadoddi, Lake 44	24938.48	660.09	740.24	28	1.34	1932.19	711.89	28.35
6	Near Inorapalya, Lake 43,	97611.38	1335.35	763.72	25	0.42	1299.28	732.93	30.79
7	Near Hejjala, Lake 42,	54536.44	903.84	784.45	24	1.70	1974.40	737.20	47.26
8	Near Kaniminike, Lake 40	42802.71	827.29	768.90	21	1.17	1007.02	734.45	34.45
9	Kumbalagodu Pond	62992.29	1086.60	767.07	20	0.59	924.64	737.80	29.27
10	Mallathahalli kere	267236.42	2244.63	842.38	5	0.69	1627.79	823.78	18.60
11	Near Hemmigeपुरa, Lake 12,	103301.08	1306.13	784.15	17	0.41	188.59	779.57	4.57
12	Near Jettiganahalli, Dry, Lake 13,	47794.45	992.06	814.94	16	0.30	2239.03	782.32	32.62
13	Mylasandra Lake	37398.43	743.68	800.91	15	0.71	592.56	787.80	13.11
14	Dubasipalya kere 2	58295.98	1096.81	808.84	11	0.60	859.30	799.09	9.76
15	BDA Layout Kere,Papareddypalya	16869.72	574.51	846.34	4	0.80	754.60	836.89	9.45
16	Nayandanahalli kere	58296.26	1155.68	817.07	8	1.98	336.64	814.33	2.74
17	Roshannagar kere	12055.52	454.43	825.00	7	0.42	276.82	821.95	3.05
18	Near Rajarajeshwari Temple, Lake 48,	10450.88	481.03	806.10	12	0.32	491.53	796.95	9.15
19	Near Kenchenahalli Road, Bangalore,	29104.50	797.68	814.33	10	0.31	1110.51	806.10	8.23
20	Hosakerehalli Kere	231857.38	2299.61	834.45	9	0.90	1376.94	810.06	24.39
21	Kengeri Gollahalli Lake	48419.01	1018.11	783.54	19	0.27	968.58	770.43	13.11
22	Near Varahasandra, Lake 11	63198.40	1013.38	800.00	18	0.88	1674.60	773.48	26.52
23	Near Lingapura, Lake 19	36551.79	765.87	726.52	27	2.52	1328.59	714.94	11.59
24	Near Kumbalagodu, Lake 18	43186.05	847.87	739.63	26	0.66	1372.29	728.05	11.59
25	Hosakere Lake	134458.84	2069.69	803.35	13	1.17	1116.20	789.02	14.33
26	Devagere Lake	42867.79	864.91	761.28	22	1.25	2176.67	744.82	16.46
27	Kullegowdanapalya, Lake 16	13995.29	504.59	754.88	23	0.41	611.21	743.90	10.98
28	Kengeri lake	67844.32	1239.15	792.68	14	0.36	383.71	790.24	2.44

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